

Quantum Bound States and Conditional Probability

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It is sometimes stated in the literature (1) that quantum mechanics is based on conditional probabilities. If this is the case, one would expect such conditional probabilities to appear in a single particle bound state. A free quantum particle is associated with a probability to interact of $\exp(ipx)$ (linked to 2-slit interference, 1-D reflection-refraction at an n_1 - n_2 junction etc), but the kinetic energy and momentum are $p^2/2m$ (nonrelativistic) and p at all x even though each x has a different phase according to $\exp(ipx)$. The momentum is p at x , but the probability for an impulse hit at x is not the same even though its modulus is. When different probabilities $\exp(ipx)$ add in an OR situation, this leads to a spatial pattern which no longer has a modulus of 1, i.e. translational invariance is broken. Such a pattern also occurs for a single particle bound state $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$. $W(x)$ can have 0 points, but the average kinetic energy $-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W$ is not 0 at such a point. One has, on average (a statistical calculation), no average interaction at such an x point. One might ask why this should have anything to do with average kinetic energy? If one writes a conservation law: $KE_{ave}(x) + V(x) = 0$, then one considers kinetic energy interacting with potential energy. If there is no interaction at some x point for a given p (not $W(x)$ on average), then it should not be part of the conservation of energy at this point. One is only interested in kinetic energy which interacts with potential energy at each x point. Thus, $a(p) \exp(ipx) + a(-p) \exp(-ipx)$ (with $a(p)=a(-p)$) may have a 0 point at some x and so it does not have an average interaction at such a point, i.e. $p^2/2m (a(p)\exp(ipx) + a(-p)\exp(-ipx)) = 0$. As a result, in a bound state, one considers kinetic energy per $p, -p$ multiplied by the average probability ($p, -p$). Different $a(p)\exp(ipx) + a(-p)\exp(-ipx)$ ($a(p)=a(-p)$) weights in this average picture indicate the extent to which the particle interacts. This idea holds for a single $p, -p$ pair, but one must normalize over all such pairs, leading to the idea of a conditional probability. Given that \hbar/p must be "created physically" in space so to speak, one must have interaction probability which creates this physical situation even in $\cos(px) + i \sin(px)$. This leads to the idea of interaction probability being 0, positive, but <1 , or even negative and it is the interaction which allows one to consider conservation of energy with a potential $V(x)$ in the first place. As a result, one cannot include a full $p^2/2m$ if there is negative, 0 or only particle interaction. Thus, $p^2/2m$ is multiplied by $2 a(p)\cos(px) / W(x)$ for $a(p)=a(-p)$.

Single Particle Probability of Interaction

A single particle, quantum or not, travels as $x=vt$ and has momentum p and kinetic energy $p^2/2m$ at each x (nonrelativistic). The quantum feature of the particle seems to be that its impulse hit point in space is not the center-of-mass x , nor is its E interaction time t , the center-of-mass t . This yields a probability to interact in spacetime of:

$$\exp(-iEt+ipx) \quad ((1))$$

Given that this probability is linked to spacetime, one might wish to normalize in both space and time through:

$$\exp(-iEt)/\sqrt{T} \text{ and } \exp(ipx)/\sqrt{L} \text{ where } T \text{ and } L \text{ are arbitrary times ((2))}$$

Even though ((1)) governs interactions (through its resolutions \hbar/E , \hbar/p), the normalization in space recognizes temporal and spatial invariance, i.e.

$$\int dx (0,L) \exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)/L = 1 \text{ and a similar expression for } t \text{ ((3))}$$

This invariance in spacetime and the above normalization is a key idea because the resolutions \hbar/p , \hbar/E follow from the Lorentz invariant:

$$\Delta x = \hbar/p \text{ and } \Delta p = \hbar/E \text{ ((4))}$$

This suggests physical gradations in spacetime, but special relativity is consistent with $x=vt$ which implies invariance in space and time for free motion. One must somehow combine the two ideas. These forces on to use two dimensions. Each dimension demonstrates \hbar/E and \hbar/p . There is, however, a difference between $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$. The former does not distinguish between p and $-p$, while the latter does in keeping with:

$$p \text{ linked with } x'/t' = v \text{ and } -p \text{ linked with } -x'/t' = -v \text{ for two Lorentz transformations ((5))}$$

((5)) is associated with a frame moving as $-v$ for p and one moving with v , for $-p$.

It is interesting that it is the imaginary part, $\sin(px)$, which shows the difference between the two frames, as it is the complex part which ensures that there is average momentum in one direction for a wavefunction. The $\cos(px)$ part is required to create the spacetime invariance while still upholding \hbar/p . If a problem does not "care" about directional motion, as in a single bound state problem which focuses on conservation of energy, then the $\cos(px)$ may be sufficient, which is the case (and will be discussed later). For one dimensional motion, however, as in the case of 2-slit interference, the complex piece remains.

In ((2)), we argued that $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ is linked with spacetime. For a single free particle, the kinetic energy is $pp/2m$ everywhere and there is no reason to even write:

$$pp/2m \exp(ipx)/\exp(ipx) \text{ ((6))}$$

What happens if there is an OR situation and there may be multiple p values?

Multiple Momentum (p) Values

In the case of a single particle interaction, there may be multiple p values and an OR situation:

$$a(p_1) \exp(ip_1 x) + a(p_2) \exp(ip_2 x) + \dots \quad ((7))$$

p_1 and p_2 lead to two different phases in the interaction in space probability. This suggests that the two interactions are not the same. One is relative to the other and this might have an effect on average values such as p and $pp/2m$. We try to examine this in more detail because it is an unusual feature. For a single p_1 , one has $p_1 p_1/2m$ everywhere. For a single p_2 , one has $p_2 p_2/2m$ everywhere. A linear OR situation such as ((7)), however, breaks translation invariance suggesting that interaction probabilities are not linked with a unit modulus. This suggests preferred interaction regions. The reason that this is important is that if a potential $V(x)$ relies on interaction with a particle. If the particle has a spatial probability region for interaction, this affects the overall $V(x)$, i.e. one considers $V(x)W(x)$ in the Schrodinger equation. If $W(x)=0$, then the effect of the term VW is 0 (and so $EW(x)=0$ and $-1/2m d/dx dW/dx$ must also equal 0. As a result, interaction probability is important in a system with interactions, like a single particle bound state.

Conditional Probability

For a single free particle with momentum p , one does not really have the notion of conditional probability because there is a single p . In an OR case, however, there is interference as one adds to $\exp(ipx)$ s:

$$a(p_1) \exp(ip_1 x) + a(p_2) \exp(ip_2 x) \quad ((8))$$

Translational invariance is broken and even though there is some probability for p_1 or p_2 at each x , it is different and not linked with a unit modulus. This probability, however, is for an impulse hit, but it means that some x points are preferred to others which is not the case for a single $\exp(ipx)$ (which has unit modulus). In terms of interaction, it seems this is like saying that it is more likely for an interaction at some x than at others. Given that one uses conservation of energy in a single particle bound state, and each p interacts with a potential $V(x)$, and that one considers a statistical average including p and $-p$ (no time present), then two issues arise. First, for $a(p) = a(-p)$

$$a(p)\exp(ipx) + a(-p) \exp(-ipx) = 2 a(p) \cos(px) \quad ((9))$$

There are specific x points for which $\cos(px)=0$. In such a case, the unusual average scenario (p and $-p$ averaged) have no interaction at this point and so one cannot include $pp/2m$ kinetic energy adding to $V(x)$ at such a point. In fact, $\cos(px)$ generalizes this to include both partial positive kinetic energy contributions for $\cos(px) > 0$ and negative ones for $\cos(px) < 0$. $\cos(px) > 0$ but not 1 suggests that one only has a partial interaction and according only uses a partial kinetic energy as interacting with $V(x)$, i.e.

$$pp/2m \cos(px) \text{ for } \cos(px) > 0 \quad ((10))$$

For $\cos(px) < 0$ one deals with the unusual statistical average including p and $-p$ and thus removing $\sin(px)$. In such a mathematical average scenario (which does not respect forward and backwards collective motion because one is only dealing with energy conservation not following the particle in time), there is actually negative probability which means that mathematically one has an anti-interaction, i.e. kinetic energy is actually removed from x

$$p^2/2m \cos(px) \text{ for } \cos(px) < 0 \quad ((11))$$

The notion of positive and negative probability needs to exist in order to have a continuous function create \hbar/p intervals. Translation invariance for a single p ($\exp(ipx)$) is created by having $\cos(px) + i \sin(px)$. The negative probability of $\cos(px)$, however, is part of the interaction process as it is linked with spatial resolution which is important in the 2-slit experiment among others. By adding $\exp(ipx)$ with $\exp(-ipx)$, it is like one removes the motion on average, but not the intrinsic spatial resolution \hbar/p which requires such a physical marking. If one considers:

$$p \cos(px) \text{ and } -p \cos(px) \quad ((12))$$

then even though $\cos(px)$ is even, one term is the reflection of the other about the x axis, just like $\sin(px)$ and $\sin(-px)$ are reflections. In terms of momentum, the average ((12)) retains the special relativistic feature of a positive peak for $p \cos(px)$ existing at a different position than that for $-p \cos(px)$. For a single particle bound state, one focuses on energy and so does not really use ((12)), but the average momentum is still a calculable quantity and should not be overlooked.

One must remember that $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$ is a mathematical average including p and $-p$ (which removes time information and physical motion in one direction and the other). Thus, $W(x)=0$, means no interaction at x for this unusual average scenario and not that the particle cannot be at $x=0$. After all, $K_{Eave}(x)$ is not 0 for $W(x)=0$.

Given that $\exp(ip_1 x) + \exp(ip_2 x)$ changes in space, one deals with a conditional probability because for a given p , $-p$ pair, there is a normalization factor which identifies x . Thus:

$$a(p) \exp(ipx) / (\text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)) = P(p/x) \quad ((13))$$

As a result, average kinetic energy is given by:

$$K_{Eave}(x) = \{ \text{Sum over } p > 0 \ (a(p) \exp(ipx) + a(-p) \exp(-ipx)) p^2/2m \} / W(x) \quad ((14))$$

For $a(p)=a(-p)$, the term in () is $2a(p) \cos(px)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, $\exp(ipx)$ is the probability for a free particle to deliver an impulse hit at x . This follows from the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$ (we argue), but special relativity is consistent with $x=vt$

and translational invariance. One should have \hbar/p markings in space which require a physical “bunching” of something while at the same time one must preserve translational invariance. This requires two bunching functions, $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ in the following manner:

$$\cos(px) + i \sin(px)$$

The modulus accounts for translational invariance, but internal spatial resolution allows for probabilistic interaction with each slit of a 2-slit apparatus if the slits are about \hbar/p apart. Both $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$, which take on positive and negative values which are critical for a physical interaction with a 2-slit apparatus. $\cos(px)$ is an even function, but $p \cos(px)$ and $-p \cos(px)$ are mirror images of each other about the x axis. On the other hand, $\sin(px)$ and $\sin(-px)$ are mirror images about the x axis, but $p \sin(px)$ and $-p \sin(px)$ are the same.

$$\text{Thus: } (p \cos(px) + p i \sin(px)) / (\cos(px) + i \sin(px)) = (-p \cos(-px) - p i \sin(-px)) / (\cos(-px) + i \sin(-px))$$

For a free particle, kinetic energy at each x is $pp/2m$ regardless of $\exp(ipx)$. If one has an OR situation and adds $\exp(ipx)$ s, then translational symmetry is broken. Certain spatial points are preferred for interactions more than others. This feature will become associated with a normalization function.

First, however, one must calculate average kinetic energy. Given that one statistically averages $a(p)\exp(ipx) + a(-p)\exp(-ipx)$, one has $2a(p) \cos(px)$ if $a(p)=a(-p)$. This has the effect of exposing the $\cos(px)$ piece (in a mathematical average calculation). Given that energy conservation is important, one cannot have such conservation unless the particle interacts. Thus, $pp/2m$ is not the term for p , $-p$ which is added to $V(x)$. One must multiply it by the interaction intensity so to speak. If $\cos(px)=0$, there is no interaction and so even though $pp/2m$ exists, it is not considered as balancing $V(x)$ as there is no interaction. In the math average including p and $-p$, one has the case of both negative and positive values of $\cos(px)$ so one has partial positive interaction with $V(x)$ and even negative interaction. This suggests an unusual physical process which is required to establish the resolution in space of \hbar/p , we argue. Given $2a(p)\cos(px)$ as the numerator, one still need to normalize the probability to 1 by dividing by $W(x)$ which is an overall interaction probability at x and so one has a conditional probability: $\{a(p)\exp(ipx) + a(-p)\exp(-ipx)\} / W(x)$.

References

1. Gudder, S. Quantum Conditional Stochastic Process 2026
<https://www.semanticscholar.org/reader/2ee520d727461b36bce2b7ecb1457f997ecec1b1>